

MORPHOLOGICAL FEATURES OF IMPAIRED REGENERATION IN TROPHIC ULCERS IN DIABETES MELLITUS

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МОРФОЛОГІЧНІ ОСОБЛИВОСТІ ПОРУШЕННЯ РЕГЕНЕРАЦІЇ ТРОФІЧНИХ ВИРАЗОК ПРИ ЦУКРОВОМУ ДІАБЕТІ

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Summary/Резюме

The purpose of the study was to summarize current scientific data on the morphological features of trophic ulcer regeneration in diabetes mellitus and to identify the main factors responsible for impaired wound healing. An analysis of contemporary scientific literature published between 2015 and 2025 was conducted using the international scientometric databases PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, Embase, Google Scholar, and the Cochrane Library. Original articles, systematic reviews, and meta-analyses focused on morphological tissue alterations, impaired angiogenesis, cellular proliferation, and reparative processes in diabetic trophic ulcers were included in the study. The analysis demonstrated that chronic hyperglycemia, oxidative stress, diabetic neuropathy, angiopathy, and tissue hypoxia play key roles in impaired tissue regeneration. Hyperglycemia causes endothelial dysfunction, microcirculatory disturbances, and suppression of fibroblast and keratinocyte proliferative activity. Excessive production of reactive oxygen species and decreased antioxidant defense lead to structural cellular damage and chronic inflammation. Diabetic neuropathy is associated with sensory, motor, and autonomic innervation disorders that contribute to tissue trauma and ischemia. Angiopathy and hypoxia result in reduced tissue perfusion, insufficient angiogenesis, and delayed reparative processes. The obtained data confirm the multifactorial nature of impaired regeneration in diabetic trophic ulcers and emphasize the need for individualized therapeutic approaches aimed at correcting metabolic disturbances, improving microcirculation, and stimulating tissue repair processes.

Key words: *diabetes mellitus, trophic ulcer, tissue regeneration, morphological changes, diabetic neuropathy, angiopathy, oxidative stress, hypoxia, angiogenesis, wound healing.*

Метою дослідження є узагальнення сучасних наукових даних щодо морфологічних особливостей регенерації трофічних виразок при цукровому діабеті та визначення основних чинників порушення їх загоєння. Проведено аналіз сучасних літературних джерел, опублікованих у 2015–2025 рр., із використанням міжнародних наукометричних баз PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, Embase, Google Scholar та Cochrane Library. До дослідження включено оригінальні статті, систематичні огляди та метааналізи, присвячені морфологічним змінам тканин, порушенням ангиогенезу, клітинної проліферації та репаративних процесів при діабетичних трофічних виразках. У результаті аналізу встановлено, що ключову роль у порушенні регенерації тканин відіграють хронічна гіперглікемія, оксидативний стрес, діабетична нейропатія, ангиопатія та тканинна гіпоксія. Гіперглікемія спричиняє ендотеліальну дисфункцію, порушення мікроциркуляції та пригнічення проліферативної активності фібробластів і кератиноцитів. Надмірне утворення активних форм кисню та зниження антиоксидантного захисту призводять до структурного ушкодження клітин і хронізації запального процесу. Діабетична нейропатія супроводжується порушенням чутливої, рухової та автономної іннервації, що сприяє травматизації тканин та розвитку ішемії. Ангиопатія й гіпоксія викликають зниження тканинної перфузії, недостатній ангиогенез і сповільнення репаративних процесів. Отримані дані підтверджують поліфакторний характер порушення регенерації трофічних виразок при цукровому діабеті та підкреслюють необхідність розробки індивідуалізованих терапевтичних підходів, спрямованих на корекцію метаболічних порушень, покращення мікроциркуляції та стимуляцію процесів тканинної репарації.

Ключові слова: цукровий діабет, трофічна виразка, регенерація тканин, морфологічні зміни, діабетична нейропатія, ангиопатія, оксидативний стрес, гіпоксія, ангиогенез, загоєння ран.

Diabetes mellitus is one of the most prevalent chronic non-communicable diseases of today and is associated with a marked dysregulation of carbohydrate, lipid and protein metabolism and the onset of a multitude of systemic complications [1, 2, 3]. The severe and a very important complication of the disease is trophic ulcers of the lower limbs, which are caused by the complex interaction of micro- and macroangiopathy, diabetic neuropathy, chronic tissue ischaemia and metabolic disorders [4]. In addition, diabetic trophic lesions have a prolonged course, tendency to become chronic, high frequency of secondary infectious complications and significant risk of necrotic changes and amputations, greatly reducing patients' quality of life and the rates of disability and mortality [5, 6].

Diabetes mellitus-mediated impaired healing of trophic ulcers is associated with complex morphofunctional changes, from the prolongation of the inflammatory phase

to the lack of proliferation of the cells of granulation tissue and defective remodelling of the extracellular matrix [7, 8]. Damage to endothelial cells, fibroblasts, keratinocytes and macrophages is caused by chronic hyperglycaemia, oxidative stress, advanced glycation end products and impaired microcirculation, resulting in diminished angiogenesis and disorganisation of collagen fibres, as well as delayed epithelialisation [9]. Although various clinical and pathogenetic research studies have been carried out, there is still a lack of understanding regarding the morphological mechanisms involved in impaired tissue regeneration in diabetic trophic ulcers. From this point of view, research into the structural characteristics of reparative processes in tissues is important in order to deepen understanding of the pathogenesis of this complication, for the improvement of morphological diagnosis and development of pathogenetically sound ways of treating and preventing diabetic trophic lesions.

The purpose of the research was to sum up the available data on morphology of regeneration of trophic ulcers in diabetes mellitus and the main factors that may take part in the process of impaired healing.

Materials and Methods

The literature sources were analyzed to check the existing sources on the morphological aspects of regeneration trophic ulcers in diabetes mellitus. International databases (PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, Embase, Google Scholar and The Cochrane Library) were searched for scientific publications between the years 2015-2025.

It covered original articles and systematic reviews and meta-analyses which investigated diabetic trophic ulcers' morphological changes in tissue, impaired angiogenesis, cell proliferation and reparative processes. Systematisation, comparison and generalisation of scientific content were used as methods of literature analysis.

Results and Discussion

Literature review for this study has revealed that there are several interrelated pathogenic mechanisms responsible for trophic ulcer in diabetic mellitus which results in impaired healing. Chronic hyperglycaemia, oxidative stress, diabetic neuropathy, angiopathy and tissue hypoxia play a key role in the development of structural and functional changes in tissues [10, 11]. These factors contribute to microcirculatory disturbances, the dysfunction of granulation tissue cells, a decrease in angiogenesis and cell proliferation, resulting in the chronicity of the wound process and delayed wound healing.

Hyperglycaemia is one of the major disease pathogenic factors, affecting the trophic ulcer formation, the course of wound healing process and systemic complications which further decrease the ability of the tissue regeneration. Elevated blood glucose levels for extended periods can cause metabolic disorders that result in damage to the vascular wall, endothelial dysfunction

and the development of atherosclerotic changes [12]. A resulting decrease in the vascular lumen causes a decrease in tissue perfusion, decreased delivery of oxygen and nutrients to the affected tissue, and significantly delays the repair processes [13]. Hyperglycaemia alters the functional activity of endothelial cells, that are responsible for regulation of vascular tone, microcirculation and the defence mechanisms of the skin. High blood glucose also negatively impacts re-epithelialisation including protein synthesis, migration and proliferation of keratinocytes and Fibroblasts, which is important for the full healing of trophic ulcers.

One of the important mechanisms leading to the disturbance of reparative processes in diabetes mellitus is oxidative stress, and it is one of the leading factors in trophic ulcers' chronicity. Excessive production of ROS with prolonged hyperglycaemia results in the damage of cell membrane, protein and nucleic acids, as well as other structural components of tissues [14, 15]. A surplus of free radicals inhibits the functional activity of cells of granulation tissue, including fibroblasts, keratinocytes and endothelial cells, resulting in the suppression of angiogenesis, proliferation and decreased production of components of the extracellular matrix.

Patients with diabetes mellitus have also been found to have decreased activities of important antioxidant enzymes, such as glutathione peroxidase (GPx) and the superoxide dismutase (SOD) [16] that remove ROS and prevent cellular damage. Loss of antioxidant defence leads to an increase in the concentration of peroxide compounds, exacerbation of inflammatory response and development of structural tissue disruption. As a result, the regenerative process in the region of the trophic ulcer is delayed, slows down granulation tissue formation and impairs the microcirculation in this area [17].

This results in an increased oxidative stress which has a significant impact on the blood supply as well as the structure and

metabolism of peripheral nerves and thus affects all parts of the peripheral nervous system such as Schwann cells, myelinated axons and dorsal ganglion sensory neurons [18]. This, in turn, results in irreversible change to the function and form of the nervous system.

One of the most frequently seen chronic complications of diabetes mellitus is diabetic neuropathy that is found to be present in around 50% of the diabetes mellitus patients [19]. Morphofunctional disturbances of the peripheral nervous system occur in the form of disorders of sensory, motor and autonomic innervation, all of which are important in trophic ulcers and disorders of regeneration. A failure of protective reactions to mechanical damage to the skin is associated with sensory impairment and is a factor in chronic tissue trauma. Motor neuropathy causes a change in the distribution of plantar load on the plantar surface of the foot, an increase in the local pressure, occlusion of capillaries and the development of local ischaemia, progressing to tissue damage.

Tropho-angiopathy also contributes to the development of trophic lesions in diabetes mellitus, and is a risk factor for ischaemic complications and amputation. In a study of 583 patients, the prevalence of PAD was seen in patients with DM and was shown to add to the severity of DM [20]. Diabetic angiopathy is closely associated with atherosclerosis, ischaemic heart disease, arterial hypertension and other cardiovascular diseases [21]. Chronic hyperglycaemia, insulin resistance, renal-angiotensin-aldosterone system activation, oxidative stress, inflammatory reactions, dyslipidaemia, thrombosis and endothelial dysfunction are the main mechanisms underlying its development. These pathological processes together result in damage to the vascular wall, narrowing of peripheral artery lumens, decreased tissue perfusion and the development of chronic ischaemia which significantly decreases the ability to heal trophic ulcers and contributes to the chronicity of the wound process.

Microcirculatory disorders and inadequate tissue perfusion cause hypoxia which is one of the main causes of impaired healing of trophic ulcers in diabetes mellitus. Metabolism, synthesis of extracellular matrix, angiogenesis and epithelialisation processes are compromised by lack of oxygen. Exposure of skin cells (especially endothelial cells, macrophages, fibroblasts, and keratinocytes) to hypoxic conditions changes the expression of genes, and interferes with normal repair processes [22].

Conclusions

Diabetic trophic ulcers have a multifactorial etiology and are related to the hyperglycaemia, oxidative stress, neuropathy, angiopathy and hypoxia. All these result in delayed healing, inadequate granulation, delayed angiogenesis, disruption in collagen fibers and inability of repair cells. Hyperglycaemia is a major contributor to these changes, both directly and indirectly affecting healing processes.

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